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**Reconciliation
Socio-Political Dimensions**

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Editorial

Today we live in a world where there is growing violence whether it be perpetrated by the so-called terrorists or those who oppose them. Faced with this conflictual situations humans wonder if there is a way out of this spiral of violence.

It is in this context that we see a ray of hope emerging from the recent developments in South Africa. After the demolition of the hated apartheid, the people of South Africa set out on a journey of national reconciliation. This novel experiment in socio-political management seems to hold a promise of peace for people everywhere in the world. That is why we have chosen as the theme of this issue of *Jnanadeepa: Reconciliation: Socio-Political Dimensions*.

The first article of this issue discusses at some length the *Truth and Reconciliation Commission* set up in South Africa to bring about national reconciliation. The author inquires into the nature and functioning of this commission and points out its positive achievements as well as its inadequacies. He then reflects on the relevance of this experiment for us in India today.

A second article develops a Gandhian perspective on reconciliation. The author traces the significant and prophetic role Gandhi played in bringing about reconciliation between the Hindus and the Muslims during the dark and violent days of the partition of India. He also calls attention to the spiritual strength that Gandhi drew from religion.

Then there is an article on forgiveness written from the perspective of women. The author points how forgiveness is often prematurely and inappropriately expected of women who have been victims of rape and battering. She describes how rape and battering cause traumatic suffering to the victims. In its pastoral approach to these victims, the church should make it clear that what has happened is unjust and so unacceptable and stand for a reconciliation based on justice for the victims. It should also learn to respect women's body-right as well as their right to be concerned about their own well-being. Only if the church fulfils these conditions has it got any right to ask women who are victims of such crimes to forgive their perpetrators.

There is an article which brings out the socio-political implications of the sacrament of reconciliation. The author points out how right from the early days of the church the social and communitarian dimensions of this sacrament has been emphasised. In fact the healing of community relationships that were broken along with a conversion of heart towards God was the primary reason for celebrating the sacrament of reconciliation.

Included in this issue is an interview with Mr. Tushar Gandhi, the grandson of the Mahatma. Tushar Gandhi advocates interreligious dialogue and collaboration to usher in a bright future for our country. He believes that religion cannot be delinked from politics because it is connected with very thing human. What he finds reprehensible is playing politics by using religion.

There are three articles on violence in this issue though which written for the last issue were kept back for technical reasons. The first of these looks upon September Eleven as a metaphor of tragedy and transgression. It suggests that in order to move away from war and violence we have to give up the exploitative myth which lays stress on 'doing' on mastery. Instead we need to adopt an explorative myth which emphasizes 'discovery' and is open to mystery. Peace is in the last analysis a gift given to those who are open to the way of the Spirit.

The second article examines the relation between religion and violence and comes to the conclusion that most of the violence in the world is caused not by religion but by the nation-state. He also shows why and how religious discourse is used to legitimise the violence perpetrated by other agencies. The third article is a moral theological reflection on violence. After showing that violence is largely the result of injustice, the author pleads for a culture of non-violence and prudent pacifism as a viable Christian option.

There is finally an article on Regional Councils. After showing how regional councils significantly contributed to the growth and vitality of the Church in the first millennium, the author asks us not to look at them as museum pieces of merely historical interest. Not should we try to reproduce them in precisely their former shapes. Rather they offer possibilities of adaptation and creativity, just as they were adaptable and creative in their own day.

It is our fond hope that the readers will find this issue of *Jnanadeepa* with a variety of articles interesting and enlightening.

Kurien Kunnumpuram SJ
Editor